

ESSENTIAL ROLE OF BRADIKININ IN THE COURSE OF BASIC LIFE PROCESSES

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Sarkisova Victoria Vladimirovna.

Lecturer at the Samarkand Medical Institute

Numonova Amina Aslamovna

Student of the Faculty of Medicine of the Samarkand
Medical Institute

Annotation: *Kinins are polypeptides formed from a 2-globulins in blood plasma under the influence of the enzyme kallikrein (kallikrein-kinin system). Most famous of them are bradykinin and kallidin.*

Bradykinin, as a member of the kinin group of proteins, is a physiologically and pharmacologically active peptide with vasodilatory properties. Due to its specific action, blood vessels expand and blood pressure drops. It is important to note that his actions are local in nature. This feature of the peptide is currently widely used in pharmacology for the treatment and prevention of heart failure and arterial hypertension.

With discovering of an increasing number of processes under the influence of bradykinin and related diseases, as well as due to the extreme relevance of the topic due to the COVID-19 pandemic, at the moment the topic needs extensive research.

Key words: *bradykinin, bradykinin storm, kinins, vasodilator, COVID-19, hypotension, inflammation, humoral regulation*

Relevance. In 2018 Russian researcher Natalya Lapina, with her colleagues from the University of Heidelberg, conducted an experiment on 42 male laboratory rats of the Sprog-Dawley line weighing 300-350 g, to study the effect of bradykinin. As result they discovered the role of the peptide in brain recovery after ischemia. It turned out that bradykinin relaxes the walls of the vessels of the brain and improves the blood supply to its damaged regions. The group of scientists concluded that it helps to restore the functioning of the cerebral vessels after focal ischemia. Also in September 2020, a group of American scientists led by Joe Roche, relying on an analysis of the expression level of all genes of COVID-19 patients in comparison with gene expression in patients of the control group, discovered new aspects in the pathogenesis of COVID-19. The explanation for many of the symptoms of patients with COVID-19 was an elementary

increase in the level of bradykinin, which is currently called the bradykinin storm.

Main part. The peptide was found in the brain of rabbits and studied by a group of Brazilian scientists under the leadership of M. Rocha e Silva in 1948. Moreover, its hypotensive properties were discovered practically in the same period.

The vasodilatory effect of bradykinin is almost 10 times greater than the effect of histamine and equally extends to the vessels of skeletal muscles and internal organs, including the coronary vessels. But this substance is unstable, bradykinin acts only for a few minutes. Its inactivation occurs with the participation of the enzyme carboxypeptidase, also called a converting enzyme. Interesting to note that this enzyme plays an extremely important role in the activation of angiotensin.

Bradykinin is produced in the kidney (a characteristic feature of the kidney is the secretion of a large amount of biologically active substances), in the lacrimal and sweat glands, where it locally expands the vessels of the skin. It is also secreted by basophils and mast cells. Mast cells and basophils play an extremely important role in some types of allergic reactions because the specific type of antibody that causes these reactions - immunoglobulin E (IgE) - has the specific ability to attach to mast cells and basophils.

When the specific antigen subsequently reacts with the specific IgE antibody, the resulting attachment of the antigen to the antibody causes the mast cell or basophil to rupture and release very large amounts of histamine, bradykinin. In inflamed tissues mast cells mainly release bradykinin. The first stage of the five main stages of inflammation is the release from damaged tissues of substances that activate the inflammation process, such as histamine and bradykinin. It is believed that kinins play a specific role in the regulation of blood flow and fluid release from the capillary bed at the site of inflammation. It is also believed that bradykinin is a natural factor that is involved in the regulation of blood flow in the vascular system of the skin, as well as the salivary glands and the glands of the gastrointestinal tract.

As the reader knows, there are several regulatory mechanisms of vital activity in the human body. Bradykinin is one of the components of regulation by means of tissue hormones. The kinin group, to which bradykinin belongs, are tissue hormones. They occupy an intermediate position between hormones and metabolites as humoral regulation factors (paracrinia). These substances have a regulating effect on tissue cells by

changing their biophysical properties (membrane permeability, their excitability), the intensity of metabolic processes, the sensitivity of cellular receptors, the formation of second intermediaries. As a result, the sensitivity of cells to nervous and humoral influences changes. Therefore, tissue hormones are called modulators of regulatory signals: they have a modulating effect. Tissue hormones are formed by non-specialized cells, but they act through specialized cellular receptors.

We can also note the participation of bradykinin in the humoral regulation of gastrointestinal activity. It enhances the motility of the small intestine together with gastrin, serotonin, motilin, HCC, histamine, substance P, vasopressin and oxytocin, acting on myocytes and neurons of the enteral nervous system. Recent studies have shown possible causes of increased blood supply during gastrointestinal activity. Some glands of the gastrointestinal tract release two kinins into the wall of the digestive tract — collidin and bradykinin, at the same time they secrete their secret into the lumen of the digestive tube. These kinins seem to cause significant vasodilation of the mucous membrane that occurs during secretion.

The kinin system is a single system with the process of blood clotting and fibrinolysis, the complement system. Its initial component, the Hageman factor, is activated on a negatively charged surface and, through a series of cascading enzymatic reactions, leads to the conversion of bradykinogen into bradykinin, which dramatically increases the permeability of capillaries and promotes the attraction of phagocytic cells to the focus of inflammation from the blood. At rest, only 25-30% of the capillaries of their total number function in many tissues, and when active, their number increases - for example, in skeletal muscles up to 50-60%. The permeability of the vascular wall increases under the influence of histamine, serotonin, bradykinin, apparently due to the transformation of small pores into large ones. Bradykinin causes both an increase in capillary permeability and a significant expansion of arterioles. For example, injection of 1 mcg of bradykinin into the human brachial artery causes an increase in blood flow in the upper limb by at least 6 times. An even smaller amount of bradykinin injected locally into the tissues causes local hyperemia and edema, since there is an increase in the permeability of the capillary wall. Bradykinin also plays an important role in the regulation of osmotic pressure and fluid volume in the body along with natriuretic hormone, natriuretic factor, plasmakinins, parathyroid hormone.

By the beginning of the new century, humanity was faced with a global problem. The COVID-19 virus infection initially broke out in several foci of

infection, but quickly spread to all corners of the globe. The virus not only spread with great speed, but also began to mutate with no less speed. Nowadays, scientists are increasingly discussing the bradykinin storm hypothesis, which explains many of the oddities of COVID-19. The bradykinin storm explains many of the symptoms of patients with COVID-19:

- The formation of blood clots in COVID-19 can be explained by the ability of bradykinin to affect blood clotting;
- A high concentration of bradykinin causes vasodilation with subsequent hypotension, bradykinin makes the vessels more permeable, and with COVID-19, the toes swell, but most importantly, fluid accumulates in the lungs. In addition, increased permeability of the vascular wall leads to greater migration of immune cells and increased inflammation;
- Supercomputer simulations have shown that bradykinin can increase the production of hyaluronic acid. Tissue fluid with hyaluronic acid forms a hydrogel in the lumen of the alveoli - perhaps because of this, artificial ventilation of the lungs sometimes does not bring relief;
- Bradykinin is able to break the blood-brain barrier protecting the brain, and this would explain the neurological symptoms of patients;
- Recently, symptoms of hyperthyroidism have been described in patients with COVID-19. Bradykinin can also have an effect on the thyroid gland, causing the described symptoms;
- Perhaps because of bradykinin, men are more susceptible to complications than women. Some key genes encoding the components of RAAS are located on the X chromosome. The double "stock" of their product to some extent compensates for the intervention of the SARS-CoV2 virus;
- New data indicate the ability of bradykinin to increase the concentration of tissue plasminogen activator, increasing the risk of bleeding in patients with COVID-19;

If bradykinin really plays such an important role, then with COVID-19, you can try medications that prevent this protein from acting.

Materials and methods: Analysis of statistical data based on the official websites of Tass Nauka, the Federal State Budgetary Institution NATIONAL Medical

RESEARCH CENTER OF CARDIOLOGY" of the Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation and the publishing house "Internauka"

Results and discussions: In the summer of 2018, Russian researcher Natalia Lapina, with her colleagues from Heidelberg University (Germany), studied how receptors for the signal peptide bradykinin help restore the functioning of brain vessels after focal ischemia. It turned out that of the two

types of bradykinin receptors, mainly one — B2 - is responsible for the relaxation of blood vessels. She published her scientific article in the journal PLoS ONE.

42 male laboratory rats of the Sprag-Dowley line weighing 300-350 g were used in the work. They were made a small hole ("window") in the skull above one of the points of the right hemisphere. A miniature Doppler device was inserted into it to assess the blood supply to brain tissues fed by the middle cerebral artery. Then the scientists tied one of the internal carotid arteries (located in the neck) to rats with a special thread to disrupt the blood flow in the middle cerebral artery of the right hemisphere. After two hours, the thread on the internal carotid artery was untied and for 22 hours, blood circulation was restored in the tissues of the right hemisphere, that is, reperfusion occurs.

After a day of observation, the brain of rats was extracted and the right and left middle cerebral arteries were separated from it. They were placed in a solution with a salt composition close to blood. A substance blocking one of two types of bradykinin receptors was added to it: in half of the cases it was a B1-receptor antagonist, in half it was a B2-receptor antagonist. After half an hour, the toxin U46619 was injected into the solution, causing narrowing of blood vessels, and after some time, bradykinin itself was injected in concentrations from 10^{-12} to 10^{-5} mol / L. Miniature devices measured how the tension of the walls of the middle cerebral arteries changes after each of the described effects. In addition, there was also a control group of animals in which ischemia and reperfusion were not caused, but their middle cerebral arteries after removal from the brain were studied in exactly the same way as described above.

The researchers also assessed the extent of brain tissue damage caused by local ischemia and subsequent restoration of blood circulation. To do this, they stained the slices with substances reacting to the presence of molecules - markers of disruption of nerve cells due to lack of oxygen (or its excess, which occurred during reperfusion).

It turned out that bradykinin had no effect on the vessels of animals from the control group (without ischemia and reperfusion): they did not relax when this signal peptide was added to the solution. However, it caused dilation of the middle cerebral arteries in animals that had their vessels disrupted, and this was all the more noticeable the greater the concentration of the peptide used. The effect of bradykinin was manifested only when it acted on a vessel from the hemisphere to which blood access was blocked by ligation of the corresponding internal carotid artery.

Bradykinin had no effect on the degree of contraction of the middle cerebral arteries if a B2 receptor antagonist was added to the solution supporting them. The introduction of a B1-receptor antagonist did not reduce the effectiveness of bradykinin.

In the spring, American scientist Joe Roche proposed a mechanism that explains many of the vagaries of the disease - the bradykinin storm. At first, few people paid attention to Roche's hypothesis, but now it has more and more supporters. It is believed that complications with COVID-19 begin due to another storm, cytokine. A recent study showed that there are a lot of cytokines in the severe form of COVID-19, but noticeably less than in patients in a similar condition due to other infections. And in another study, it turned out that the drug tocilizumab, which neutralizes inflammatory molecules, did not reduce mortality among COVID-19 patients, although in theory it should have. Perhaps it's not just the cytokines.

Severe inflammation can be caused by high levels of bradykinin and its derivative DABK. These proteins are produced by cells infected with the virus. The more cells are infected, the more of these proteins. It was also Roche who revealed that bradykinin can explain not only inflammation, but also the main symptoms of infected people. Based on his hypothesis, bradykinin antagonists began to be used. For example, ikatibant was given to several patients — the results are promising, but it's too early to judge. Now icatibant is going to be tested during full-fledged clinical trials. The advantage of this drug is that it has long been known and approved for use, and the patent for it has expired, that is, any pharmaceutical company can produce it.

A step forward in the study of the bradykinin storm hypothesis was helped by the Summit supercomputer, which, since the summer, has processed information on the expression of more than 160,000 mRNAs from 9 COVID-19 patients and 40 healthy people. The process, which included the analysis of 2.5 billion genetic combinations, took more than a week. Data analysis allowed us to formulate a hypothesis about how COVID-19 affects the body - the so-called "bradykinin hypothesis". With COVID-19, bradykinin is produced in excess: blood vessels literally begin to "leak", which leads to the accumulation of fluid in all tissues of the body, including the lungs.

According to Ancha Baranova, professor at the School of Systems Biology at George Mason University, the effect of bradykinin still needs to be studied. According to her, without any COVID-19, increased bradykinin production is observed in people with a hereditary tendency to angioedema. This is a serious disease when people can swell greatly due to

stress, and this condition often threatens their lives. With coronavirus, even if there is no hereditary disease, the viral load on the body in some cases can "bend" a completely healthy system so much that the patient will develop a condition resembling an angioedema crisis.

Conclusion: Since the discovery of bradykinin and its specific properties, scientists have been discovering more and more processes that it affects. Of course, bradykinin has extensive physiological and pharmacological effects. This feature is very beneficial to scientists, who today see it as a solution to a huge number of problems. Since 2018, a huge number of experiments have been conducted to clarify the role of bradykinin not only in normal physiological processes, but also in the pathogenesis of particularly dangerous diseases. Of course, scientists recommend not to abuse this knowledge, warning against suddenly relying only on new data on the bradykinin storm in the treatment of the disease. However, the main breakthrough in the study of the effect of bradykinin on the body has been made. Perhaps in the near future, based on this knowledge, a new model of perception of the body and new methods of treatment of both congenital and acquired diseases will be created.

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